

TRIBOLOGY PROPERTY AND ELECTRICAL RESISTIVITY OF C/C COMPOSITES WITH BACTERIAL CELLULOSE

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ABSTRACT

The fabrication methods of the BP-C/C composites with Bacterial Cellulose (BC) and Bamboo charcoal Particle (BP) as Si additive. The effect of BP mass content on the wear and friction properties has been investigated experimentally. The composite specimens were prepared by carbonizing the BP/BC/Phenol FRP plates at the temperatures of 700°C to 1000°C. The dry sliding wear test for the composites was carried out against the SUS304 counter face by using a pin on drum type tribology apparatus. From the wear test results, the wear and friction properties of the BP-C/C composites were dependent on BP mass content and carbonizing temperature. The composites with 5wt% BP carbonized at 900°C indicated the lowest friction coefficient of 0.15 among the composites. On the other hand, the composites with 5wt% BP carbonized at 1000°C exhibited the lowest wear rate of 2.25×10^{-10} [mm²/N]. The experimental results also indicated that BP can be applied as fillers which can provide lower wear and friction properties to the composites.

Formation of thin coating film with C/C composites will be discussed by using some experimental results according to the morphology of the surfaces observed by SEM. The PV values of C/C composites for their durability were examined, and a new evaluation method proposed by the Authors found to be valid for PV values of C/C composites. Furthermore, in order to apply the C/C composite to the carbon brush of DC motors, the basic experiments were conducted for clarifying tribology properties of the developed materials under current conduction and thermal condition. As the results of the sliding tests with Oxygen Free Copper (OFC) as a friction mating material, the coefficient of dynamic friction took the high value over 1.0. In addition, the electrical resistivity of composite was measured at the room temperature, and its mean value was 2.72×10^{-4} Ωm.

1 INTRODUCTION

Bacterial Cellulose (BC) synthesized by *Acetobacter Xylinum* is one of the eco-friendly materials, and so called "Cellulose Nano Fibers (CNF)". The fibrous structure of BC is three-dimensional nano scale network of microfibrils which are about 100 times thinner than plant celluloses and artificial carbon fibers [1-3]. By using Direct Impregnation Method (DIM), we have already investigated the wear and friction properties of C/C composites with Bacterial Cellulose (BC) and phenol resin, and the carbonizing temperature effect on tribology properties were clarified under no lubricant dry sliding condition with SUS304 rotor [4, 5]. Its specific factor of wear element loss of 10^{-10} order and its dynamic friction coefficient of about 0.2. In addition, in the use of electrical equipment field, the development of brushes which must have high wear resistance is desired strongly.

In this study, in order to improve their tribology properties and a new application to the practical use for current conduction/friction material such as DC motor brush, the fabrication method of the C/C composites with Bamboo charcoal Particles (BP) [6] as Si additive is developed. And, the effect of mass content of BP on tribology properties is investigated experimentally under dry sliding condition. The tribology properties of composites are discussed according to the morphology of worn and fracture surfaces observed by SEM and EDS analysis.

For the PV value of the material durability, the formation of thin coating film with C/C composites on the base material is discussed by examining some experimental results. Furthermore, a new evaluation method is proposed to evaluate the validity for PV values of C/C composites. We also

performed the sliding test for the C/C composite under non conduction with the rotor of Oxygen Free Copper (OFC) as a friction mating material.

2 MATERIALS AND TESTING METHOD

2.1 Materials preparation

Bamboo charcoal Powder contains hydrophobic micro-particles that are subject to aggregation in an aqueous environment, and this characteristic may make bamboo charcoal difficult to be uniformly dispersed in the matrix. On the other hand, due to extremely low volume content of the BC cellulose nanofibers, the porosity of BC ranges from 92% to 94%. Nevertheless, mean gap sizes of the texture vary within less than $2\mu\text{m}$ [4, 5]. Therefore, BP must be milled by ball-miller into size of less than $2\mu\text{m}$ to disperse BP into gaps of BC microfibrils network. Figure 1 shows material design image of the BP-C/C composites desired.

To start with fabrication, a commercial BP was firstly grinded by a pestle and mortar into the size of less than 10 mm. In the next step, the BP was ball-milled by using Fritsch P-7 ball mill by zirconia balls with 10mm, 5mm and 1mm at 480 rpm, respectively. BP was milled into size of less than $1\mu\text{m}$ from SEM observation.

Moreover, in this study, BC gel was milled by mixer to get fine size of BC and to improve an issue of sparse or dense in the BC fiber. Figure 2 shows SEM observation of the milled BC (mBC). This figure indicates that BC possesses the sparse and layered microfibrils structure, thereby the milled BC could be effective on reinforcing the BP-C/C composites. The ratio of the BC fiber in the BC gel was measured to determine the BC fiber content in the C/C composites. By calculating the weight of BC fibers in the mBC gel, the C/C composite containing any ratio of BC fibers can be produced.

In order to clarify the effect of BP wt% content on the tribology properties, BPs with 1wt%, 5wt% and 8wt% were mixed into the mBC gel, where the weight content of BC microfibril was constant of 1wt% in phenol resin.

Figure 1: Material Design of BP-C/C Composites.

Figure 2: SEM observation of milled BC.

Figure 3: Summary of DIM for C/C composites.

Generally, it is difficult to impregnate the hydrophilic mBC gel with the hydrophobic phenol resin. By using the Direct Impregnation Method (DIM) [4, 5] shown in Fig. 3, the phenol resin is gradually impregnated into three-dimensional microfibril network of the mBC gel, microfibril gaps and dispersed BP when the alcohol is evaporated with water molecules. In the first stage, the resol type phenol resin diluted with the alcohol of the half weight of phenol resin and the prepared mBC gel were mixed well, and a mixture was degassed in a vacuum dryer at the earlier stage of drying. After the mixing process, the BC/Phenol resin mixture was dried in the room condition, and then, heated and hardened at 35°C for 3~4 weeks obtain the BC/Phenol resin Pre-impregnation (BP-BC/Phenol resin pre-preg). After this procedure, The pre-preg was pressed at pressure of 1MPa and 160°C, and degassed several times for 1~2 minutes, and then pressed for 30 minutes to obtain the BP-mBC/Phenol resin FRP plates.

Before carbonizing process, the BP-mBC/Phenol resin FRP plate was cut into a size of the specimens corresponding to each experiment. The samples were held at 120°C for an hour, and then were heated up from 120°C to carbonizing temperatures (700-900°C) with heating rate 10°C/h, finally, they were kept at the desired temperature for an hour. By the carbonizing process of the FRP plates, BC microfibrils changed into the carbon fiber of nano-scale, and the phenol resin of the matrix became the glassy carbon. Finally, the FRP plates were carbonized into the “BP-C/C composites”.

2.2 Tribology test for C/C composites

In order to evaluate the tribology properties of the C/C composites, the sliding tests were conducted with the pin-on-drum type tribology tester [4]. The rotor made by SUS304 or OFC were used as friction mating materials. A specimen was slid over the rotor drum surface with roughness of $R_a=0.3\ \mu\text{m}$. The testing specimen of $3.5\text{mm}\times 3.5\text{mm}\times 2.0\text{mm}$ was prepared by using grinding machine. The sliding surface of the specimen was polished with grinding papers of 1200 grit and had $0.3\ \mu\text{m}$ of polishing surface before the test.

The sliding conditions were as follows: sliding speed 1.5m/s, sliding distance 130km, contact pressure 1MPa or 0.6MPa and non-lubrication condition. In order to mate the surface of the specimen with the curved surface of the rotor, the tests were started after the specimen slid on the rotor for about 24 hours. The torque converter is equipped to the tribology tester for measuring friction force.

In order to determine the wear volume, the wear thickness of specimen was measured by a laser displacement equipment, and the wear volume was calculated with the dimensions of specimens. The specific factor of wear element loss K [mm^2/N] is derived from Eq. (1);

$$K = W / PL \quad (1)$$

where W is the wear volume [mm^3], P the normal load [N], and L the sliding distance [mm].

The dynamic friction coefficient μ was given by Eq. (2):

$$\mu = T / PR \quad (2)$$

where T is the value of friction torque [Nm], and R the radius of the rotor [m].

The PV value which is given by the normal pressure load P and the moving velocity on the surface V [m/s], indicates the property of durability for sliding material. The sliding test for PV value was conducted by the sliding machine of pin-on-drum type. The test condition were as follows; sliding speed 2.0[m/s], and applied load 13[N] at the start and with applied load step with 4.9[N/h]. The specific wear rate w [mm²] is derived by Eq. (3).

$$w = W / L \quad (3)$$

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Tribology test results for BP-C/C composites

From the results of tribology test for specimens carbonized at 700°C with 8wt% BP, no valid results could be obtained from the wear test due to high friction condition. This might be caused because of the bad fabrication due to high content of filling BP and low carbonizing temperature.

Figure 4 shows the value of the specific factors of wear element loss against BP wt% at carbonizing temperatures. The composites with 5wt% BP had the lower wear rate of $2.25 \times 10^{-10} \sim 6.02 \times 10^{-10}$ [mm²/N] as clearly shown in this figure. The specific factors of wear element loss of the BP-C/C composites was closely correlated with not only BP wt%, but also carbonizing temperature. It was considered that carbonization degree and microstructure of the composites were changed, and the composites can have the higher bonding strength between reinforcements and matrices.

Figure 5 shows mean dynamic friction coefficients against BP wt% at different carbonizing temperatures. The mean dynamic friction coefficients of composites varied between 0.14 ~ 0.22 and these depend upon carbonizing temperature and BP wt%. The lowest friction coefficient of 0.14 was obtained for the specimens at 900°C with BP 5wt%.

Figure 4: Mean specific factors of wear elements loss K against BP wt% with parameters of different carbonizing temperatures.

Figure 5: Mean dynamic friction coefficient μ against BP wt% with parameters of different carbonizing temperatures.

Figure 6: Worn surfaces of the composites carbonized at 1000°C with different wt% BP; (a) 0wt% (C/C composites), (b) 1wt%, (c) 5wt%, and (d) 8wt% BP.

3.2 Surface observation on BP-C/C composites

In order to clarify the effect of BP dispersion contents on the wear and friction mechanism, we observed the worn surfaces of specimens carbonized at 1000°C with 0wt% (C/C composites), 1wt%, 5wt% and 8wt% BP contents and, as shown in Fig. 6.

On the worn surface of specimens with 0wt% BP (C/C composites), cracks with several micrometers length were induced, and many BC microfibrils were observed inside and around of the cracks. For worn surface of 1wt% BP specimen in Fig. 6(b), BC microfibril pull-outs were observed, and the surface became smooth. The worn surface of 5wt% BP specimen (Fig. 6(c)) was smooth, and there were still some microcracks. When the BP content reached at 8wt%, the surface became rough and severe abrasive wear occurred on the worn surface shown in Fig. 6(d). When the composites have high BP content of 8%, the surface fractures and formation of the wear debris tend to increase on worn surfaces due to lower bonding strength between BP and matrix, and then higher wear rate was exhibited.

3.3 Consideration on wear and friction characteristics of the other composites

In order to clarify BC microfibril effect on the wear and friction mechanism, BP/C composites with phenol resin and BP 5wt% were developed, and the wear and friction properties were compared to these for C/C composites and BP-C/C composites.

The difference in the friction coefficient must be due to the influence of the reinforcement materials and the difference in the microstructure caused by BP wt% and carbonizing temperatures. The SEM observations for the worn surfaces of specimens of C/C composites, BP-C/C composites with 5wt% BP, and BP/C composites are shown in Fig. 7. For the worn surface of C/C composites in

Figure 7: SEM images of worn surface of developed composites carbonized at 1000°C; a) C/C composites, (b) BP-C/C composites (5wt%BP) and (c) BP/C composites.

Fig. 7(a), the several deep scratches and cracks of few micrometers in length were observed. The crack propagation was suppressed due to BC fiber bridging [5]. In the case of the BP-C/C composites shown in Fig. 7(b), the fine wear debris were observed on the worn surface. Due to these wear debris, the friction coefficient of BP-C/C composites was increased in the case of that at 1000°C. Furthermore, the worn surface seems to be smooth and the BC bundles were observed on the surfaces. On the worn surface of the BP/C composites in Fig. 7(c), the severe abrasive wear was observed on the worn surface of 5wt% BP. Because of the generation of a large amount of wear debris, the entrapped wear debris depended on the sliding materials, which were increased the wear rate.

3.4 Evaluation of a thin film coating of C/C composites and their PV values

By examining the durability of material, the formation of thin coating film with C/C composites on the base material is done by the layered method. Figure 8 shows the thin film coating layer of BC/Phenol FRP composite with 2wt% BC on the base of Phenol resin before carbonizing. After carbonizing at 900°C, the BC/Phenol FRP composite layer was changed into the C/C composites on the carbonized Phenol resin (CPR) specimens, its thickness became the one third of original one.

The change of the wear rate of thin film coating is shown in Fig. 9. A new evaluation method which is the two line estimation method by using the log-log scale diagram, was applied to the evaluation of the PV values of thin film coating of C/C composites. From the examination for friction, the wear rate for each specimens is increased as increasing applied load by following the Archard's law. It is found that the new method proposed by the Authors is valid for the evaluation of PV values. From another experiment which is not shown due to the limit of space, the dynamic coefficient was found to be decreased as increasing the applied load. The dynamic coefficient is dependent on the true contact area, applied load and the sliding force. The dynamic coefficient is the ratio of the sliding force divided by the true contact area, the true contact area arise and sliding loads decrease with increasing applied load, and then, the dynamic coefficient of friction would be decreased.

From the experimental results, the limit PV value was obtained to be 4.05[MPa m/s] for thin film coating of C/C composite on the CPR specimens. This value is slightly lower than the value of 4.76[MPa m/s] for the CPR without a coating film in the previous report. From the SEM observation for the worn surface of thin coating film specimens, small cavities and the drop off debris were observed, then the improvement would be required for a better fabrication method of thin coating film.

Figure 8: Optical microscopy view after carrying out drying at 160°C.

Figure 9: Change of wear rate against load with log-log scale.

3.5 Tribology test results for with the OFC rotor and electrical resistivity

The sliding tests of the C/C composite for current conduction materials was performed with the rotor of Oxygen Free Copper (OFC) as a friction mating material. Figure 10 shows photographs of mBC/Phenol resin pre-preg, phenol resin FRP and a testing specimen.

In the results of sliding tests with the SUS304 rotor, the C/C composites in this study have the almost same level of the specific factor of wear element loss of 10^{-10} order as the previous research work. On the other hand, in the case of the OFC rotor used, the specific factor of wear element loss took higher value than that in the case of the SUS304 rotor. The hardness value of C/C composite is larger than the OFC material, and then the OFC rotor was also attacked by the C/C composites.

As can be seen from Table 1 and Fig. 11, the specific factor of wear element loss of the C/C composite was 3.63×10^{-9} and the value of coefficient of dynamic friction was exceeding 1.0 under the non-conducting condition. The reason for high coefficient of dynamic friction is considered due to the two elements abrasive wear between the C/C composite and the OFC rotor of a friction mating material, and/or the three elements abrasive wear with the additional influence of the debris from the OFC rotor or the C/C composite.

Specimens	K [mm ² /N]	Average of μ	Rotor type	Pressure [MPa]
BC-S10-1	4.97×10^{-10}	0.18	SUS304	1.0
BC-S10-2	8.25×10^{-10}	0.23	SUS304	1.0
BC-S06-5	9.10×10^{-10}	0.33	SUS304	0.6
BC-C06-6	3.63×10^{-9}	1.32	OFC	0.6
BC-C06-7	2.36×10^{-9}	1.16	OFC	0.6

Table 1: Experimental results of sliding tests.

(a) mBC/Phenol resin pre-preg (b) mBC/Phenol resin FRP (c) Testing specimen
 Figure 10: Photographs of mBC/Phenol resin pre-preg, phenol resin FRP and testing specimen.

Figure 11: Change of dynamic friction during the sliding tests for mBC-C/C composites.

The contact surface of the C/C composite is shown in Fig. 12. For the specimen BC-S10-1 and BC-S06-5 (Fig. 12(a)), there were little wear debris and damage in the sliding test with the SUS304 rotor. On the other hand, from viewing the photographs in Fig. 12(b), the specimen BC-C06-7 contacted with the OFC rotor had a rough surface, and many scars were observed on the surface because of high load caused by high coefficient of dynamic friction. Furthermore, the wear debris of C/C composite and/or the OFC rotor were made and accumulated in the scars on the contact surface.

To examine the debris on the specimens, the SEM observation was performed and its result was shown in Fig. 13. It can be seen from these photographs that the debris was accumulated on the contact surface of C/C composites. Particularly, the debris from the OFC rotor was accumulated and gathered in the cracks and voids on the surface and pressed together by contact load.

Figure 12: Photographs of contact surfaces of mBC-C/C specimens.

Figure 13: SEM photographs and EDS analysis of contact surface of C/C composites.

The test specimens for measurement of electrical resistivity were prepared in the dimensions of 30~50mm×5.0mm×3.0mm. The measurement was performed at the room temperature by using the four terminals method in Fig. 14. The electrical resistivity ρ [Ωm] of C/C composite was calculated by Eq. (4):

$$\rho = \frac{A}{L} \frac{V_S}{V_R} R \quad (4)$$

where A is the cross sectional area of composite [m^2], L : the distance of the probes of the digital multi meter [m], V_S : the difference of the electric potential [V], V_R : the difference of electric potential of the standard resistor [V] and R : the value of resistance of standard resistor [Ω]. In order to offset the influence of the thermo-electromotive, the measurement of V_S was done by inverting the polarity of the current. The value of V_S by Eq. (4) was obtained as the average of the values before and after inverting the polarity.

The average of the electrical resistivity of C/C composite is $2.72 \times 10^{-4} \Omega\text{m}$ and is higher than the carbon brushes used for the industrial motors. A reference example of the resistivity of the carbon brushes used for the DC motors is $0.4 \sim 0.8 \times 10^{-4} \Omega\text{m}$ [7]. The carbon materials or the commercial C/C composites are made by taking the impregnation process and the carbonizing process repeatedly. The reason for high value of the resistivity of the C/C composite is considered because of the coarse material structure. In the fabrication of developed C/C composite, the voids might be generated in curing process of the phenol resin or carbonizing process, and would be remained in the inside of the materials because the impregnation process and the carbonizing process were conducted only once.

In order to examine the thermal influence, the heating value Q_F for the sliding tests was estimated. The heating value by the frictional heat was given by Eq. (5);

$$Q_F = \mu P v \quad (5)$$

where μ is Coefficient of dynamic friction, P : Normal load [N], and v : Sliding speed [m/s].

The heating value Q_E by the electrical current was given by following equation;

$$Q_E = I^2 \rho L / A \quad (6)$$

here I indicates Electrical current [A], L : Length of specimen [m], and A : Cross-sectional area [m^2].

In this study, the heating value of thermal influence by frictional heat would be larger than that by electrical current. As the coefficient of dynamic friction is larger, the larger Q_F is resulted. In order to reduce the frictional heat, it is necessary to improve the tribology properties of the C/C composite.

Figure 14: Four terminals method for measurement of electrical resistivity of C/C composites.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the fabrication method of the BP-C/C composites with a new structure by using BC of Cellulose Nano Fiber (CNF) and Bamboo charcoal Particles (BP) was successfully developed. Some application of C/C composites were performed for the thin film coating on the base material, and the sliding test with the OFC rotor and their electrical resistivity. The results obtained were as follows:

- (1) The specific factor of wear element loss and friction coefficients were dependent on BP content and carbonizing temperature. The BP-C/C composites with 5wt% BP exhibited better wear and frictional properties in comparison with C/C composites and BP/C composites. It can be concluded that the bamboo charcoal powder combined with carbonized BC fibers played an important role in increasing the bonding strength among BP, carbonized fibers and matrices, and had an effect on the wear resistance of the BP-C/C composites.
- (2) Formation of thin coating film with C/C composites was discussed by using some experimental results with the morphology of carbon fibers on the worn surfaces. A new evaluation method proposed by the Authors is found to be valid for evaluation of PV values of C/C composites.
- (3) The sliding tests of the C/C composite were conducted with OFC rotor as a mating material, and the coefficient of dynamic friction took the value over 1.0. The tribology characteristics of C/C composite with the OFC are found to be the two elements abrasive wear between the composite and the OFC rotor and the three elements abrasive wear with the adding influence of the debris from the OFC rotor and/or the C/C composite.
- (4) The electrical resistivity of the C/C composite at the room temperature was $2.72 \times 10^{-4} \Omega\text{m}$ and higher than the carbon brushes used for the DC motors because of the material construction caused by the impregnation process and the carbonizing process.

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